

1. Why does DDC 16 edition called phoenix schedules?

Ans :

The 16th edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) is referred to as the Phoenix Schedules because it was a major reconstruction of the classification system following a significant loss of materials.

A fire in 1933 at the Library of Congress destroyed many of the records and materials related to the Dewey Decimal Classification system.

After the fire, efforts were made to rebuild the classification system, particularly focusing on restoring and revising schedules and tables. This revision marked a rebirth or renewal of the DDC.

The phoenix, a mythical bird, is associated with rising from its ashes, symbolizing renewal and revival. The DDC 16th edition was similarly "reborn" after the devastation caused by the fire.

This significant restoration and modernization of the classification system led to the 16th edition being popularly referred to as the Phoenix Schedules.

2. Why DDC index is called related index?

Ans:

The index in the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) is called a "relative index" because it relates terms and concepts across different parts of the classification system, regardless of their specific position within the schedules.

Examples:

The DDC system is divided into **ten main classes** (e.g., 500 for Science, 600 for Technology).